

FedLoss: In-Region Location Verification in 6G Networks via Personalized Federated Learning

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Abstract—In wireless networks, in-region location verification (IRLV) refers to the problem of verifying whether a transmitting device is inside a region of interest, based on the channel estimated from the received signal. In this paper, we consider multiple regions of interest and multiple base stations (BSs), each locally performing IRLV with a machine-learning (ML) model on estimated channels. We exploit the spatial correlation of channels and adopt a federated learning strategy among the BSs. Still, we also want to obtain different local models to reflect the different statistics of observed channels. We propose **FedLoss**, a personalized federated learning framework tailored to physical-layer IRLV under non-IID channel conditions. **FedLoss** operates in two phases: a federated averaging stage that learns a shared representation across BSs, and a locally regularized fine-tuning stage that adapts the global model to each BS’s channel statistics. A loss-based switching criterion determines the transition between the two phases, enabling efficient and stable training. We evaluate the proposed approach using realistic 3GPP-inspired channel models in a multi-base-station 6G scenario.

Index Terms—Physical-layer in-region location verification; Federated learning; 6G networks; Channel state information.

I. INTRODUCTION

In-region location verification (IRLV) has emerged as a promising security mechanism for future 6G networks, as it exploits the inherent randomness of wireless propagation to infer the transmitting area of the device. This information can be used, for instance, for authentication purposes, without relying solely on cryptographic credentials [1]. In dense and heterogeneous deployments, multiple geographically separated BSs can jointly observe the wireless channel and collaboratively infer whether a received transmission originates from an authorized location or device. Such collaboration is particularly attractive in scenarios where a single BS has limited observations or faces unfavorable channel conditions.

A fundamental challenge in this distributed setting is that the channel-state-information (CSI) observed by different BSs is intrinsically heterogeneous, as they experience distinct channel statistics due to differences in geometry, propagation paths, and local scattering environments. As a result, learning-based classification models trained at different BSs rely on non-identically distributed (non-IID) data [2]. Federated learning

(FL) has recently gained significant attention as a framework that enables multiple devices to collaboratively train a shared model without explicitly exchanging raw data [3]. This privacy-preserving feature is well-suited for collaborative CSI-based classifiers, as sharing raw CSI would leak information on the user (e.g., its location). In a standard FL setup, each client performs local training and periodically uploads model updates to a central server for aggregation. Among the various aggregation strategies, FedAvg is the most widely adopted due to its simplicity and effectiveness under IID data assumptions [4]. However, it is now well understood that FedAvg can suffer severe performance degradation in the presence of non-IID data distributions across clients [5]. Addressing non-IID data heterogeneity remains an active area of research, and several approaches have been proposed, including surveys on heterogeneous federated optimization [6]. The application of federated learning to physical-layer IRLV is still in its early stages. Prior works have explored collaborative authentication, e.g., in constrained IoT scenarios using FedAvg [7] and federated learning for Wi-Fi fingerprinting or localization [8]. However, these studies typically rely on either global models or heuristic aggregation strategies, which may be ill-suited for the highly heterogeneous multi-BS environments.

In this paper, we study a distributed physical-layer IRLV scenario with multiple BSs and users located in a set of areas. Each BS independently aims to infer the region from which the user transmission occurs based on its own observed CSI only. This is an IRLV problem with multiple regions and multiple verifiers. The verification is performed by using a local ML model applied to the locally observed CSI. However, the training of the local models is performed in a *federated* fashion among the BSs. This allows us to exploit the spatial correlation of the wireless channels: indeed, the same region is observed from a different perspective by each BS, and the propagation effects (including reflectors and scatterers) associated with a single region have a similar behavior for different BSs. To effectively exploit shared information across BSs while respecting their heterogeneous channel statistics, we propose *FedLoss*, a personalized federated learning framework tailored to physical-layer IRLV. **FedLoss** combines an initial federated averaging phase to learn a shared representation with a locally regularized fine-tuning phase that adapts the model to each BS.

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Fig. 1: Simulated scenario with classification error probability.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- i) We formulate distributed physical-layer IRLV as a classification problem under inherently non-IID CSI observations across multiple BSs.
- ii) We propose FedLoss, a personalized federated learning framework that addresses channel-induced data heterogeneity through local fine-tuning around a shared global model.
- iii) We evaluate the proposed approach using realistic 3GPP-inspired channel models and demonstrate its superiority over standard federated and non-federated baselines, particularly in data-scarce and highly heterogeneous environments.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a wireless network consisting of E geographically distributed BSs, each equipped with a uniform linear array (ULA) of M antennas. Each user is equipped with a single antenna. Users can be in a set of predefined spatial regions, denoted as *areas* a_n for $n = 1, \dots, N$. Each legitimate user is authorized to transmit from a specific region, and in the following, we denote as Alice the generic legitimate transmitter. An adversarial transmitter (Trudy) seeks to impersonate Alice by transmitting from one of the spatial areas, with the constraint that she cannot access the true area used by Alice. Fig. 1 shows an example of the considered scenario, where squares represent the $N = 6$ regions, and triangles identify the BSs.

To verify that users transmit from their authorized regions, the BSs act as independent in-region location verifiers, denoted as b_e for $e = 1, \dots, E$. For verification purposes, Alice and Trudy send pilot signals; each BS observes distinct channel realizations due to differences in geometry, propagation environment, and noise. The task of the BSs is to determine the area from which the received signal originated. Trudy seeks to impersonate Alice by transmitting from one of the spatial areas, with the constraint that she cannot access the true area used by Alice. This is the problem of IRLV, which aims at

verifying whether a user is inside a region of interest. In our specific scenario, we have *multiple regions of interest*, and we aim at distinguishing which region the transmitter is transmitting from. Each BS will independently decide the region of transmission, on the basis only of its own channel observations. The IRLV is performed by local ML models that are, however, trained in a *federated* fashion among the BSs. This lets us take advantage of the spatial correlation among wireless channels: each base station views the same area from a different angle, so the propagation characteristics – including reflectors and scatterers – within that region exhibit similar behavior across the various base stations.

Channel Model: Let $\mathbf{p}_e \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denote the known position of BS b_e , and let $\mathbf{p}_j \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denote the position of a generic transmitter (Alice or Trudy). The distance between the transmitter and BS b_e is $d^{(e,j)} = \|\mathbf{p}_e - \mathbf{p}_j\|$. We adopt a clustered frequency-selective channel model based on 3GPP specifications [9]. Under this model, even in line-of-sight (LOS) conditions, the received signal at a BS arises from L propagation rays (or paths), each characterized by an angle of arrival (AoA) and a propagation delay. For the ℓ -th path, the AoA at BS b_e for transmission from \mathbf{p}_j is

$$\xi_\ell^{(e,j)} = \xi^{(e,j)} + \Delta_\ell, \quad (1)$$

where $\xi^{(e,j)}$ is the nominal AoA between \mathbf{p}_j and b_e , and $\Delta_\ell \sim \mathcal{U}(-\xi_{\text{sp}}, \xi_{\text{sp}})$ represents the intra-cluster angular spread. We assume orthogonal-frequency-division-multiplexing (OFDM) signaling employing N_S subcarriers. At subcarrier index k , the received signal at BS b_e upon transmission of a pilot symbol x from position \mathbf{p}_j is

$$\mathbf{y}^{(e,j)}(k) = \mathbf{h}^{(e,j)}(k)x + \mathbf{w}^{(e,j)}(k) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{h}^{(e,j)}(k)$ is the single-input multiple-output (SIMO) channel vector and $\mathbf{w}^{(e,j)}(k) \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_w^2 \mathbf{I})$ is additive Gaussian noise.

The channel vector is composed of LOS and non-LOS (NLOS) components,

$$\mathbf{h}^{(e,j)}(k) = \sqrt{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa+1}} \mathbf{h}_{\text{LOS}}^{(e,j)}(k) + \sqrt{\frac{1}{\kappa+1}} \mathbf{h}_{\text{NLOS}}^{(e,j)}(k), \quad (3)$$

with Rician factor $\kappa \geq 0$. The LOS component aggregates the contributions of the L rays as

$$\mathbf{h}_{\text{LOS}}^{(e,j)}(k) = \sum_{\ell=1}^L \gamma^{(e,j)} \boldsymbol{\beta}(\xi_\ell^{(e,j)}) e^{-j2\pi k \Delta f \tau_\ell^{(e,j)}}, \quad (4)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta}(\theta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{M}} [1, e^{j\pi \sin \theta}, \dots, e^{j\pi(M-1) \sin \theta}]^T$ is the ULA steering vector, Δf is the OFDM subcarrier spacing, and $\gamma^{(e,j)} = \frac{c}{4\pi f_c d^{(e,j)}}$ is the free-space pathloss coefficient with carrier frequency f_c and speed of light c . The path delay for the first ray is $\tau_0^{(e,j)} = d^{(e,j)}/c$, and intra-cluster delays are

$$\tau_\ell^{(e,j)} = \tau_0^{(e,j)} + \Delta\tau_\ell, \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta\tau_\ell \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 2c_{\text{DS}})$ is uniformly distributed within a bounded cluster delay spread. The NLOS components are modeled as

$$\mathbf{h}_{\text{NLOS}}^{(e,j)}(k) \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, (\gamma^{(e,j)})^2 \mathbf{I}), \quad (6)$$

i.i.d. across antennas and subcarriers.

In this paper, we assume a unit-power pilot transmission, i.e., $\mathbb{E}\{|x|^2\} = 1$, thus the per-subcarrier signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is

$$\text{SNR}^{(e,j)} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{\|\mathbf{h}^{(e,j)}(k)\|^2\}}{\mathbb{E}\{\|\mathbf{w}^{(e,j)}(k)\|^2\}} = \frac{L(\gamma^{(e,j)})^2}{\sigma_w^2}. \quad (7)$$

The complete channel frequency response (CFR) matrix for BS b_e and transmitter position \mathbf{p}_j is

$$\mathbf{H}^{(e,j)} = [\mathbf{h}^{(e,j)}(1), \dots, \mathbf{h}^{(e,j)}(N_S)] \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N_S}. \quad (8)$$

Each area a_n is a square region of side length S_A centered at position \mathbf{p}_n . Fig. 1 illustrates an example with $N = 6$ areas and $E=4$ BSs.

Dataset Description: Each BS b_e collects N_c independent channel realizations per area, yielding a local dataset of size $C = N_c N$. The dataset is defined as

$$\mathcal{D}_e = \{(\mathbf{H}^{(e,i)}, a^{(i)}) \mid i = 1, \dots, C\}, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{H}^{(e,i)}$ is the channel matrix in (8) corresponding to the i -th example, i.e., where the transmitter is in area $a^{(i)}$. Here, we assume that perfect channel estimates are available for training.

Attacker Model: We assume the set of areas $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^N$ is common knowledge to all parties, including Alice, the BSs, and the adversary –Trudy. When Alice transmits from area a_n , Trudy may attempt to impersonate Alice by transmitting from any other area a_m with $m \neq n$. We therefore model Trudy as having access to $N - 1$ alternative areas. The goal of the BSs is to correctly classify the actual area of transmission and thereby reject signals from unauthorized regions.

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

We now formalize the *Data-Driven Distributed Classification for Physical-Layer IRLV* (3D-RV) problem in the multi-base-station wireless setting introduced in Section II. In the 3D-RV problem, E geographically distributed BSs observe frequency-selective channel measurements generated according to the channel model described in Section II. Each measurement consists of a channel frequency response matrix $\mathbf{H}^{(e,i)} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N_S}$, collected at BS b_e , and an associated area label $a^{(i)} \in \{a_1, \dots, a_N\}$ indicating the true region from which the pilot signal originated. The goal of the distributed detection problem is to learn, in a data-driven fashion, a set of classifiers $\{\theta_e\}_{e=1}^E$ that map channel measurements to area labels, while allowing a central decision maker (or fusion center) to infer the legitimacy of a transmission by combining the decisions of all BSs. Directly sharing raw CSI data across BSs is impractical due to privacy, communication overhead, and regulatory constraints. Therefore, we adopt a federated learning paradigm in which each BS trains locally on its own dataset \mathcal{D}_e and shares only model updates with a central aggregator. A key difficulty arises from the intrinsic heterogeneity of the channel observations across BSs. Because each BS is located at a different position \mathbf{p}_e with respect to the transmitter positions \mathbf{p}_j (see Section II), the distributions

of the channel matrices $\mathbf{H}^{(e,i)}$ vary significantly across e . Such physics-induced non-IID data distributions degrade the performance of standard federated learning algorithms (e.g., FedAvg [4]) that rely on a single global model being effective across clients.

Formally, let $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \{\theta_e\}_{e=1}^E$ denote the set of local model parameters, where θ_e defines a classifier at BS b_e . Each BS b_e has access to its local dataset \mathcal{D}_e as in (9) consisting of $C = N_c N$ labeled examples generated according to the channel model in Section II. The objective of the distributed detection problem is then

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}^* = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \frac{1}{E} \sum_{e=1}^E \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{D}_e; \theta_e), \quad (10)$$

where $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{D}_e; \theta_e)$ denotes the empirical multi-class cross-entropy loss of classifier θ_e evaluated on \mathcal{D}_e . Crucially, the optimization must be carried out without sharing the raw datasets \mathcal{D}_e across BSs.

IV. PROPOSED SOLUTION: FEDLOSS

Algorithm 1 The proposed solution: FedLoss.

Require: Local datasets $\{\mathcal{D}_e\}_{e=1}^E$, initial model $\theta_G^{(0)}$, epochs T , window T_E , threshold \mathcal{L}_{\min} , regularization λ

Ensure: Personalized models $\{\theta_e^*\}_{e=1}^E$

- 1: Initialize global model $\theta_G^{(0)}$
 - 2: **for** round $t = 1$ to T **do**
 - 3: **for** each BS b_e **in parallel do**
 - 4: Update local model $\theta_e^{(t)}$ on \mathcal{D}_e
 - 5: Compute local update $\Delta\theta_e^{(t)}$
 - 6: **end for**
 - 7: Aggregate: $\Delta\theta_G^{(t)} \leftarrow \frac{1}{E} \sum_{e=1}^E \Delta\theta_e^{(t)}$
 - 8: Update global model: $\theta_G^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \theta_G^{(t)} + \Delta\theta_G^{(t)}$
 - 9: **for** each BS b_e **do**
 - 10: Evaluate switching criterion using $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{D}_e; \theta_G^{(t+1)})$
 - 11: **if** criterion met **then**
 - 12: Mark b_e ready for fine-tuning
 - 13: Store its global model $\theta_G^{(T_e)} = \theta_G^{(t+1)}$
 - 14: **end if**
 - 15: **end for**
 - 16: **if** all b_e marked for fine-tuning **then**
 - 17: **break**
 - 18: **end if**
 - 19: **end for**
 - 20: **for** each BS b_e **do**
 - 21: Fine-tune: $\theta_e^* \leftarrow \arg \min_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{D}_e; \theta) + \lambda \|\theta - \theta_G^{(T_e)}\|_2^2$
 - 22: **end for**
 - 23: **return** $\{\theta_e^*\}_{e=1}^E$
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To tackle the 3D-RV problem described in Section III, we propose FedLoss, a federated learning framework designed to handle heterogeneous data distributions across BSs. FedLoss operates in two main stages:

- 1) **FedAvg Phase**– *Collaborative Representation Learning*:
In this initial stage, the BSs jointly train a shared global

model θ_G using an iterative federated averaging procedure. At each communication round t , each BS b_e updates its local model based on its own dataset \mathcal{D}_e and computes a local model update $\Delta\theta_e^{(t)}$ of the current global model $\theta_G^{(t)}$. These updates are aggregated at a central server to refine the global model:

$$\Delta\theta_G^{(t)} = \frac{1}{E} \sum_{e=1}^E \Delta\theta_e^{(t)}, \quad (11)$$

followed by

$$\theta_G^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \theta_G^{(t)} + \Delta\theta_G^{(t)}, \quad (12)$$

which is then sent to all BSs. This phase continues until a convergence criterion is met, at which point the global model captures a representation that is broadly useful across all BSs despite their heterogeneous CSI distributions.

- 2) **Fine-Tune Phase – Personalized Fine-Tuning:** As described later, each BS decides when to stop the first phase. Let $\theta_G^{(T_e)}$ be the global model available at this stopping time. Then, BS i refines the model using its own local dataset, resulting in a personalized model θ_e^* . The fine-tuning solves:

$$\theta_e^* = \arg \min_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{D}_e; \theta) + \lambda \|\theta - \theta_G^{(T_e)}\|_2^2, \quad (13)$$

where λ is a regularization parameter that balances local adaptation against fidelity to the global representation.

The pseudocode for FedLoss is presented in Algorithm 1.

A central element of FedLoss is the *switching criterion* between the collaborative and fine-tuning phases. Since prematurely switching to fine-tuning may lead to suboptimal personalization and excessive switching may waste communication rounds, we monitor the training loss of the global model. Specifically, at each BS b_e , we track the average loss reduction over a sliding window of T_E communication rounds. If the improvement falls below a predefined threshold \mathcal{L}_{\min} , the BS transitions to local fine-tuning. Formally, a switch occurs at time $T_e = t_0 + T_E$ when, for the first time

$$\frac{1}{T_E} \sum_{t=t_0}^{t_0+T_E-1} \left[\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{D}_e; \theta_G^{(t)}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{D}_e; \theta_G^{(t-1)}) \right] < \mathcal{L}_{\min}.$$

A. Convergence and Robustness of FedLoss

For analytical insight, we specialize in the binary case with two BSs, which exposes how heterogeneous channel statistics can make the pooled distribution less separable than the local ones. In the remainder of the section, let us define θ_{avg} , θ_{gl} , and θ_{loss} as the models— at convergence, of FedAvg, global (or centralized) model, and FedLoss. Note that by the centralized model θ_{gl} we refer to an ML model trained on the union of all BS datasets; in the IID case, it would outperform all the other models, indeed, it violates the privacy assumptions of federated learning. Note that if the statistics of channel observations under the two classes are available, we have a classical binary hypothesis testing problem, which is optimally

solved by the likelihood ratio test (LRT) according to the Neyman-Pearson theorem.

We now obtain the following result.

Theorem 1 (FedLoss robustness for two BSs and two regions): Consider the 3D-RV problem in Section III with $E = 2$ BSs and $N = 2$ transmission regions. Let P_e and Q_e denote the class-conditional distributions of the channel features observed at BS b_e under regions a_1 and a_2 , respectively (i.e., $\mathbf{H}^{(e)} \sim P_e$ under a_1 and $\mathbf{H}^{(e)} \sim Q_e$ under a_2). Let θ_e^* be the personalized model obtained by the FedLoss fine-tuning phase with a given parameter λ :

$$\theta_e^* = \arg \min_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{D}_e; \theta) + \lambda \|\theta - \theta_G\|_2^2, \quad e \in \{1, 2\}.$$

Then the following holds:

- 1) (*Convergence of personalization*) For any $\lambda > 0$, the fine-tuning objective is strongly convex in θ (for convex loss functions), and gradient-based fine-tuning converges to the unique minimizer θ_e^* for each BS.
- 2) (*Consistency limits*) As $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, $\theta_e^* \rightarrow \theta_{\text{gl}}$ (global model); as $\lambda \rightarrow 0$, θ_e^* approaches the solution of purely local training at BS b_e .
- 3) (*Robustness to conflicting BS statistics*) Suppose the pooled/global training distribution mixes the two BS observations,

$$P_{\text{mix}} = \frac{1}{2}(P_1 + P_2), \quad Q_{\text{mix}} = \frac{1}{2}(Q_1 + Q_2).$$

If the global mixture becomes weakly separable in the sense that $D_{\text{KL}}(P_{\text{mix}} \| Q_{\text{mix}})$ is small while at least one BS remains locally separable (e.g., $D_{\text{KL}}(P_1 \| Q_1)$ or $D_{\text{KL}}(P_2 \| Q_2)$ is not small), then a single global classifier trained on the pooled data can suffer degraded discrimination, whereas FedLoss can recover locally discriminative decision rules.

Proof: Items 1)–2) follow from standard properties of ℓ_2 -regularized empirical risk minimization: the quadratic term makes the personalization objective strongly convex (for convex hypothesis classes), guaranteeing uniqueness and convergence of gradient descent; the limits $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ and $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ follow by inspection of the objective. For Item 3), note that pooling heterogeneous observations induces the mixture distributions P_{mix} and Q_{mix} , whose separability can be smaller than that of individual BS distributions. In extreme *conflict* cases (e.g., approximately swapped class-conditionals across BSs), P_{mix} and Q_{mix} can become nearly indistinguishable even when each BS individually preserves discrimination. Since the collaborative phase targets a single shared representation, it may inherit this reduced separability. The fine-tuning phase mitigates the conflict by reverting toward local solutions when needed (small λ), while still leveraging the shared representation through the regularization term. ■

We also have the following result establishing the connection between the considered classification problem and the corresponding hypothesis testing problem.

Corollary 1: As dataset sizes go to infinity ($C \rightarrow \infty$), and the models are either neural networks (NNs) or least-square support vector machines (LS-SVMs), the local models

Fig. 2: Normalized confusion matrices: true labels on the vertical and predicted labels on the horizontal axes.

converge to the optimal Neyman-Pearson tests with local observation statistics.

Proof: The result is an immediate consequence of the results of [2]. ■

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

To validate the effectiveness of FedLoss, we compare it with three baselines, named Global, Single, and FedAvg, considering all the possible transmitting positions of both Alice and Trudy. In the Global case, there is a “virtual” single base-station (BS) that has a dataset containing all the BS data. This is optimal if the datasets were formed by IID data, i.e., when the BS were located close enough to one another. In the Single case, on the other hand, all the BS train on their own dataset, even if small. This approach is supposed to work well when the BSs are far from each other; thus, sharing local information is damaging the overall performance. Finally, in FedAvg, the BS perform the FedAvg algorithm. For testing the performance, each client has available a test dataset drawn from its own distribution \mathcal{D}_e . The Global is also tested on datasets drawn from \mathcal{D}_e separately, and not on the pooled version. The scenario we used for our simulations is depicted in Fig. 1, where $E = 4$ BSs collaborate to classify signals coming from $N = 6$ areas. The parameters we used to generate the channels are the following: a constant $\text{SNR}^{(e,j)} = 6 \text{ dB}, \forall e, j$, $\xi_{\text{sp}} = 6 \text{ deg}$ and $c_{\text{DS}} = 5 \text{ ns}$, from 3GPP specifications [9]. Each BS has available $N_c = 32$ datapoints per class, thus a total of $N_c N = C = 192$ samples for training.

Network Architecture: To validate the proposed framework, we employed a standard ResNet-18 convolutional-neural-network (CNN) as a backbone [10], with a two-layer fully-connected head. This is a standard architecture, which makes our findings replicable and verifiable. For training, we used a batch size of 32 samples, weight-decay of 35×10^{-5} and learning rates of 10^{-3} for Global and Single, while 5×10^{-4} for Federated. Batch sizes and learning rates were found via grid search for each method, ensuring fair comparison.

Security Analysis: Fig. 2 shows the confusion matrices of the proposed method FedLoss and the three baselines, averaged across BSs. These matrices are used to evaluate the security performance. In fact, assuming Alice is in a position in the area a_n and Trudy is in a position in the area a_m , we find the probability that Trudy is misled by Alice by looking at

Fig. 3: Accuracy VS Epochs for Single, Global, FedAvg, and the proposed FedLoss.

the entry (n, m) , $n \neq m$ of the confusion matrix. In other words, off-diagonal elements of the confusion represent the probability that Trudy fools the system. On the diagonal, we find the accuracy, which can be interpreted as the probability of correctly classifying Alice. By inspecting the matrices, we see the superiority of FedLoss over all the baselines. The heatmap of Fig. 1 shows the classification error probability.

Accuracy VS Epochs: Fig. 3 shows the average accuracy across the BSs as a function of the number of training epochs when the average distance between BSs is $D_{\text{bs}} \simeq 1.1 \text{ km}$. We notice that both Global and FedAvg perform poorly, as expected, since we see from Fig. 1 that the BSs are very far from each other, leading to very non-IID datasets across the BSs. The Single performs well despite the small training dataset, but it gets outperformed by the proposed FedLoss, which achieves the best accuracy across all the methods.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented FedLoss, a novel federated learning framework that tackles the non-IID dataset issue common in standard federated learning algorithms by performing local fine-tuning. The switching time between the federated and the fine-tuning phase is determined by monitoring the training loss. We numerically evaluated its performance using realistic channel models in terms of accuracy, showing its superiority both over state-of-the-art federated and standard non-federated algorithms.

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